

A CASE REPORT ON THE MANAGEMENT OF MEIBOMITIS WITH SHUNTHYADI

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ABSTARCT

Meibomitis which is inflammatory condition of meibomian gland of eyelid. It is common disease of eyelid seen in practice. This case report presents the management of meibomitis using Shunthi, Nimba Patra, Saindhav Pindi, a traditional ayurvedic treatment. The patient showed significant improvement in symptoms such as inflammation of meibomian gland eyelid, Irritation, Itching within one week of treatment. This study highlights the potential of Ayurvedic interventions in ocular disorders and encourages further clinical research.

KEYWORDS: Meibomitis, Pindi, Nimba Patra, Shunthi, Saindhav, Ayurveda, Shakalyatantra.

INTRODUCTION

This case report explores the Ayurvedic perspective on meibomitis, a condition characterized by inflammation meibomian gland the eyes. These glands are responsible for

secretion of the lipid layer of tear film which prevents rapid evaporation of tears and maintains ocular surface stability. Dysfunction or inflammation of these glands leads to altered secretion, blockage of gland orifices and subsequent ocular discomfort. Common causes include bacterial infection, poor lid hygiene and environmental factors. Conventional treatment mainly includes warm compresses, lid hygiene and topical medications, but recurrence is common, prompting exploration of Ayurvedic interventions. The treatment involve use of Pindi containing Shunthi, Nimba Patra, Saindhav. This report highlights the therapeutic potential of Ayurvedic eye treatments and encourages further research to validate these traditional practices in contemporary clinical settings.

The report focuses on the management of meibomitis using Shunthyadi Pindi, a traditional Ayurvedic treatment. This study intends to correlate traditional Ayurvedic principles with contemporary clinical findings, offering useful insights into effective therapeutic approaches for the management of Meibomitis.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate efficacy of Shunthyadi Pindi in management meibomitis.
- To study meibomitis in details

CASE REPORT

A 30 year old male patient, visited the Salakya Tantra OPD of our Ayurveda hospital. He complaints mild redness, irritation, itching since 1 week. The symptoms were gradual in onset and were associated with mild redness of the eyelid margin.

Visual Acuity: 6/6 OU

General Examination: Pallor – Absent; Icterus – Absent; Cyanosis – Absent; Clubbing – Absent; Lymphadenopathy – Non palpable; Oedema – Absent; BP – 120/80 mmHg; Pulse – 76 bpm.

Systemic Examination: CVS, CNS, RS, GIT – No abnormality.

Local Examination

- Head posture: straight and erect
- Facial symmetry: normal
- Ocular posture: visual axes parallel

- Eyelids: OU- Mild congestion and edema, meibomian gland orifices were blocked, with thickened oily secretions expressed on digital pressure. Mild tenderness over the lid margin was present
- Conjunctiva: congestion present
- Cornea: normal
- Iris: normal pattern
- Pupil: round, central, reactive
- Lacrimal apparatus: normal

TREATMENT GIVEN

The patient was treated with Nimba Patra Saindhav Shunthi Pindi as a local therapeutic procedure. Under aseptic condition fresh Nimbapatra crushed using mortar and pestle. In this Shunthi Churn was added and also pinch of Saindhav and mixed evenly. Afterward the paste was mild heated (Sukhoshna) then the paste is evenly packed in cotton cloth and applied over the affected eyelid in the form of Pindi. Until the Pindi cools down. Post-treatment care included cleaning eye with cotton soaked in warm water.

The treatment was administered once daily for 7 days. The patient was advised to maintain proper lid hygiene and avoid rubbing the eyes. Symptoms such as itching, irritation, redness and lid swelling were assessed before and after treatment.

TREATMENT GIVEN	SHUNTHYADI PINDI
MATRA	1 KOL
KAL	ONCE A DAY
DURATION	7 DAYS

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Shigru patra swaras, Shunthi, Nimb patra, Saindhav.

Under aseptic condition fresh Nimbapatra crushed using mortar and pestle. In this Shunthi Churn was added and also pinch of Saindhav and mixed evenly. Afterward the paste was mild heated (Sukhoshna) then the paste is evenly packed in cotton cloth and applied over the affected eyelid in the form of Pindi.

For Literary part, text books were used. The disease studied for modern books and various cases studied in OPD. For treatment part Shunthyadi Pindi was used. Case record form and

consent form were maintained. OPD patients from our hospital diagnosed with meibomitis were observed and given treatment.

OBSERVATIONS

Symptom	Day 0	Day 2	Day 7
Inflammation of meibomian gland	+++	++	–
Irritation	++	+	–
Itching	+	+	–
Redness	++	+	–

RESULTS

Patient got total relief from inflammation, irritation, itching and redness in 1 week.

DISCUSSION

The case demonstrated significant improvement in symptoms of meibomitis following treatment with Shunthyadi Pindi. Compared to conventional treatments, this Ayurvedic approach offers a curative solution with minimal risk of recurrence.

MODE OF ACTION

Drug Name	Rasa	Vipak	Virya	Dosha Karma	Karma
<i>Shigru Patra</i> <i>Swarasa</i>	<i>Katu,</i> <i>Tikta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Kapha-Vata</i> <i>Shamak</i>	<i>Chakshushya,</i> <i>Vedanasthapaka,</i> <i>Shothagna</i>
Shunthi	<i>katu</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Kapha-</i> <i>vataghna</i>	Shitprashman, Shothhar, Vedanasthapan, Pachan
<i>Nimba Patra</i>	<i>Tikta,</i> <i>Kashay</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Shit</i>	<i>Kapha-</i> <i>pittaghna</i>	<i>Vranaghna</i>
<i>Saindhav</i>	<i>Lavan,</i> <i>Madhur</i>	<i>Madhur</i>	<i>Shit</i>	<i>Tridoshghna</i>	<i>Pachan, Netriya,</i>

Meibomitis is caused by vitiated kapha and pitta dosha, it paly major role, leading strotorodh (blockage of gland), and inflammation. And irritation is due to vaat dosh involvement. Shunthi help to open blocked gland secretion & reduce inflammation Nimba Patra has anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory actions, help in controlling infection and irritation. Saindhav help in mild scrap and reduce the stickiness.

CONCLUSION

Shunthyadi Pindi is an effective and affordable treatment for Meibomitis. This case highlights the potential of Ayurvedic interventions in managing ocular disorders, warranting further research through larger clinical trial.

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